

THE INTERCONNECTEDNESS OF READING SUBSKILLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14200723>

Annotatsiya. O'qish — bu murakkab kognitiv jarayon bo'lib, u turli xil ko'nikmalarning o'zaro bog'liqligini talab qiladi. Ushbu maqola o'qishning asosiy ko'nikmalari — dekodlash, tushunish va tanqidiy munosabatni yoritib beradi. Ushbu ko'nikmalar bir-biriga chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, o'qish jarayoni murakkablashishi davomida uning turli bosqichlarida faoliyat ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'qish ko'nikmalari, dekodlash, tushunish, tanqidiy munosabat, o'qish rivojlanishi.

Abstract. Reading is a complex cognitive procedure, which requires the association of different subskills. This article will delve into these subskills - decoding, comprehension, and critical reaction. They are highly dependent on each other and they interact together at different stages of reading development.

Key words: Reading subskills, decoding, comprehension, critical reaction, reading development.

Reading is a complex process, which requires different cognitive tasks. In recent research, it became obvious that reading is completely understood as a mastery of interconnected subskills, namely decoding, comprehension, and critical reaction. Reading is a comprehensive ability, which occurs with the help of intricate connections between the above-mentioned subskills, decoding, comprehension, and critical reaction. Understanding these connections has important implications for literacy instruction, supporting the development of effective, well-rounded readers.

Jeane S. Chall is considered to be the proponent of reading as the mastery of a progressive set of subskills. In her article “Research supports direct instruction models” she mentions the importance of phonics as a part of any reading program. In her article she mentions the terms “**skills**” and “**whole language approaches**” to **reading** and she outlines the differences between them. She characterizes Whole language as a language cognitive process, also mentioning that there are proponents of direct instruction, which define **reading** in more developmental terms. It could be described as follows:

(this goes in a subsequent order)

Decoding forms the basis of literacy. It is a simple skill, which translates written symbols into sounds and words. Jeanne Chall in her book (1983) “*Stages of Reading Development*” explains decoding as the foundational stage of reading skill. This process is foundational, as without effective decoding, readers cannot access text meaningfully.

Gough and Tunmer, in their book *Simple View of Reading*, mention decoding as the necessary step for comprehension. Studies have shown that fluent decoding is demanded in order to achieve good comprehension. It facilitates comprehension by reducing the cognitive load associated with word recognition, enabling readers to focus on understanding the text’s meaning. (Ehri, 2005)

Comprehension is the next stage of reading development, which relies on cognitive processes. Comprehension is the ability to understand and make meaning from text, relying on prediction, and schema activation. Kintsch’s (1988) “Construction-Integration Model” describes comprehension as a multi-stage process where readers construct a mental representation of the text and integrate it with prior knowledge, creating a coherent understanding.

Next stage of reading development is a critical reaction, which is mentioned as the culmination of reading proficiency. The reason for calling critical reaction the culmination, it is the highest level of reading proficiency. This skill requires readers higher-order thinking skills, which are being able to analyze, interpret, and respond to texts by considering various perspectives. Low-order and high-order thinking skills are explained in the theory of Bloom’s taxonomy:

a) lower-order (knowledge, comprehension, application)

b) higher-order (analysis, synthesis, evaluation) cognitive abilities provides a framework for evaluating and designing instructional strategies for critical thinking.

It is important to mention that decoding, comprehension, and critical reaction are closely interconnected with each other. Decoding forms the basis for comprehension, which subsequently allows for critical reaction.

Conclusion

This article highlights that reading subskills—decoding, comprehension, and critical reaction—are not learned separately from each other. They are closely

interconnected components, that reinforce one another. Educators should focus on the cognitive abilities of readers to help them become critical readers. Future research might further explore how technology and digital media impact these skills and their interconnections, as well as investigate best practices for promoting interconnected skill development across different age groups and learning contexts.

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